

Antibiotics in Endodontics

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The overuse of antibiotics and the emergence of antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains is a global concern today. Since the discovery of penicillin by Fleming in 1928, antibiotics have revolutionized the entire health-care system.

History of Antibiotics

In 1928 Antibiotics were first discovered, but clinically they were not routinely used until the early 1940s. The foundation idea for antibiotics was laid down by Paul Ehrlich by introducing the term “magic bullets” for a chemical that would attach itself to the germ and kill it. The term “antibiosis” that means “against life” for early antibacterial drugs was given by Jean Paul Vuillemin. Louis Pasteur and Robert Koch first described the term antibiotics in 1877. In endodontics antibiotics can be used in various modes. Grossman - Father of Endodontics was the first person who used the applications of local Antibiotics in endodontics. He proposed poly antibiotic paste combination (PBSC) of penicillin, bacitracin, streptomycin and caprylate sodium suspended in silicon vehicle in 1951.

Rationale of Systemic Antibiotics

There is international concern about the overuse of antibiotics and the emergence of antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains. As dentists prescribe approximately 10% of antibiotics dispensed in primary care, it is important not to underestimate the potential contribution of the dental profession to the development of antibiotic-resistant bacteria. Antibiotics do not reduce pain or swelling arising from teeth with symptomatic apical pathosis in the absence of evidence of systemic involvement. One Cochrane systematic review has found no evidence to support the use of antibiotics for pain relief in irreversible pulpitis.

Odontogenic infections, including endodontic infections, are polymicrobial involving a combination of gram-positive, gram-negative, facultative anaerobes and strict anaerobic bacteria. Endodontic infection is the infection of root canal system in which microorganisms play a prominent role in both pulpal and periapical disease. The harmful effects of

these bacteria leads to pulpal inflammation which ultimately leads to necrosis of pulp, which become reservoir of infection, characterized dead microbes and their noxious products enters the periapex leads to irritation of periapical region, that result in periradicular inflammation, leading to abscess and cellulitis. The ultimate aim of endodontic treatment is to eradicate as many micro-organisms and their by-products from the root canal space by using various antimicrobial agents to provide a micro-organism free environment.

In course of endodontic treatment antibiotics can be given either systemically or locally to aid in the host defence in the elimination of the bacteria. Narrow spectrum of antibiotics should be the choice initially due to adverse, use of broad spectrum antibiotics result in antibiotic sensitive.

Indications For the Use of Systemic Antibiotics

The increasing use of broad-spectrum antibiotics is a matter of concern even in cases where antibiotics are not indicated. Most endodontic infections are confined within the tooth and can be successfully managed by established local operative treatment.

The spectrum of endodontic pathosis includes many conditions for which dentists and endodontists determine that it is appropriate to prescribe antibiotics. Some of these conditions involve purely an inflammatory reaction, and some involve various stages of infection. This infection may be localized to the pulp and periapical tissues, and it may be spreading to regional lymph nodes, or systemically. Antibiotic sensitivity of the bacteria found within the oral cavity is gradually decreasing, and a growing number of resistant strains are being detected.

Systemic antibiotics are generally used in the indications like:

- (i) In the prevention of the spread of infection and acute periapical abscesses with signs of systemic involvement and in progressive and persistent infections.

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- (ii) Acute periapical abscesses in immuno-suppressed patients.
- (iii) Prophylaxis of infection associated with tooth avulsion.
- (iv) Treatment of persistent symptomatology and/or exudation after the performance of all available options to control inter-radicular infection.
- (v) Medically compromised patients are more susceptible to complication arising from odontogenic infections and antimicrobials have a more specific role in their treatment. Prophylaxis against bacteraemia caused by endodontic treatment in immuno suppressed patients
- or patients susceptible to bacterial endocarditis, prosthetic cardiac valves and prosthetic joint infection.
- (vi) Abscess dissemination and
- (vii) Progressive infections (rapid onset of severe infection in <24 h, cellulitis or a spreading infection, osteomyelitis) where onward referral to oral surgeons may be necessary.
- (viii) Replantation of avulsed permanent teeth
- (ix) Soft tissue trauma requiring treatment
- (x) Endodontic flare ups etc.

Indications for antibiotics as an adjunct during endodontic therapies

Pulp/Periapical condition	Clinical and radiographic data	Antibiotics as adjunct
Symptomatic irreversible pulpitis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Pain ▪ No others symptoms and signs of infection 	NO
Pulp necrosis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Nonvital teeth ▪ Widening of periodontal space 	NO
Acute apical periodontitis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Pain ▪ Pain to percussion and biting ▪ Widening of periodontal space 	NO
Chronic apical abscess	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Teeth with sinus tract ▪ Periapical radiolucency 	NO
Acute apical abscess with no systemic involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Localized fluctuant swellings 	NO
Acute apical abscess in medically compromised patients	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Localized fluctuant swellings ▪ Patient with systemic disease causing impaired immunologic function 	YES
Acute apical abscess with systemic involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Localized fluctuant swellings ▪ Elevated body temperature (>38 °C) ▪ Malaise ▪ Lymphadenopathy ▪ Trismus 	YES
Progressive infections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Rapid onset of severe infection (less than 24 h) ▪ Cellulitis or a spreading infection ▪ Osteomyelitis 	YES
Persistent infections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Chronic exudation, which is not resolved by regular intracanal procedures & medications 	YES

Conditions not requiring adjunctive antibiotics includes are:

- (i) Pain without signs and symptoms of infection.
- (ii) Teeth with necrotic pulps and a radiolucency.
- (iii) Symptomatic apical periodontitis (pain, pain to percussion and biting and widening of periodontal ligament space)
- (iv) Teeth with a sinus tract (chronic peri radicular abscess) and
- (v) In case of discrete and localized swelling, the primary aim is to achieve drainage without additional antibiotics.

Penicillin, Erythromycin, Metronidazole, Clindamycin, Clarithromycin, Azithromycin, Tetracycline, Doxycycline etc. are commonly used systemic antibiotics.

To be continued.....

